

A localized cutaneous scleroderma in woman after diatomaceous dust oral consumption: a case report

Iva Parvova¹

1 Department of Rheumatology, Medical University of Sofia, UMHAT „St. Anna“, 1, Dimitar Mollov str., Sofia 1709, Bulgaria

2 Medical center Spectro – IMA, 120 Tintyava str., Sofia 1172, Bulgaria

3 Faculty of Medicine, Sofia University “Saint Kliment Ohridski”, 1, Kozyak str., Sofia 1407, Bulgaria

4 Faculty of Chemistry and Pharmacy, Sofia University “Saint Kliment Ohridski”, 1, James Bourchier blvd., Sofia 1164, Bulgaria

5 Department of Organization and Economics of Pharmacy, Faculty of Pharmacy, Medical University of Sofia, 2, Dunav str., Sofia 1000, Bulgaria

Corresponding author: Valentina Petkova (vpetkova@pharmfac.mu-sofia.bg)

Received 13 September 2025 ♦ Accepted 1 October 2025 ♦ Published 21 October 2025

Citation: Parvova I, Zlateva P, Broshtilova V, Mihaylova V, Petkova V (2025) A localized cutaneous scleroderma in woman after diatomaceous dust oral consumption: a case report. *Pharmacia* 72: 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.72.e171959>

Abstract

Background: Scleroderma-like disorders are heterogenous diseases characterized by sclerosis of the dermis, subcutis and sometimes the underlying soft tissues and bones. The clinical course of diseases may range from a benign local disease to a widespread systemic, life-threatening disease. There is a high risk of developing a systemic disease indistinguishable from idiopathic scleroderma in miners in coal and gold mines exposed to silica dust (silicon dioxide SiO₂). Several cases of scleroderma morphea (circumscripta), a localized form with limited areas of skin sclerosis without Raynaud's phenomenon or visceral involvement, have described in response to inhalatory exposure to silica dust. A 52-year-old woman was admitted to Rheumatology Clinic for clinical investigation of skin thickening on the abdomen, chest, and proximal thighs, along with pain, redness, and mild itching, a few months after taking fossil shell dust for six months, purchased from a pharmacy in Sofia. The instructions for use state that the product is a natural mineral – not a food, medicine, or dietary supplement that can be used as an additive in animal feed (for birds and mammals) with an anti-adhesive effect, and that it has a number of applications in the food industry. The patient took a level tablespoon of the contents of the package, dissolved in a glass of water, once a day – approximately 10 g of dust. The clinical skin findings consisted of violaceous erythema-infiltrative plaques. The histological diagnosis after skin biopsy of a lesion was scleroderma circumscripta. The chemical analysis of the skin sample showed a silicon content about ten times more than normal.

Keywords

diatomaceous dust, silica dust, silicon dioxide, scleroderma, case report

Introduction

Scleroderma-like disorders are heterogeneous diseases characterized by sclerosis of the dermis, subcutis and sometimes the underlying soft tissues and bones. The clinical

course of the disease may range from a benign and localized condition to a widespread, systemic, life-threatening disease (Lorinda et al. 2006; Foti et al. 2008). Localized scleroderma, scleromyxedema, Buschke scleroderma, nephrogenic systemic fibrosis, POEMS (polyneuropathy,

organomegaly, endocrinopathy, monoclonal protein and skin changes) syndrome, myeloma with scleroderma – like changes, eosinophilic fasciitis, eosinophilia-myalgia syndrome, toxic-oil syndrome, diabetes mellitus, carcinoma syndrome and others are in this group of conditions. There is a high risk of developing a systemic disease indistinguishable from idiopathic scleroderma in coal and gold miners exposed to silica dust (silicon dioxide SiO_2) (Cowie 1987; Rustin et al. 1990; Betta et al. 1994; Bovenzi et al. 1995). It is known that occupational dust and chemical inhalatory exposure, be it through mining, stonemasonry, building or other trades, increases the risk of various systemic autoimmune rheumatic diseases including rheumatoid arthritis and systemic sclerosis. Although the pathogenic mechanisms of silica-induced autoimmunity are not elucidated fully, it is thought that alveolar macrophage ingestion of silica and the ensuing phagosomal damage is an initiating event that ultimately leads to production of autoantibodies and immune-mediated tissue injury (Rubio-Rivas et al. 2017; Nikpour et al. 2025). Several environmental hazards have been reported as triggering factors for scleroderma-like disorders – organic solvents, vinyl chloride, bleomycin, polymerizing epoxy resins, and silica; except for silica, all other substances induce changes classified as scleroderma-like disorders (Haustein et al. 1985; Bakst et al. 2009). The specific manifestation of silica dust inhalatory exposure effects may depend on underlying differences in genetic susceptibility or other environmental exposures (Parks et al. 1999). Although silica dust is often described as an occupational risk factor for diffuse cutaneous systemic sclerosis occurrence, few case reports have been published about it in relation to morphea (Pedro Gomes et al. 2017). The case report was prepared in accordance with the requirements of the CERA guidelines and after explicit informed consent obtained, while maintaining anonymity and personal data (Riley et al. 2017).

Case report

A 52 – year – old Caucasian woman presented to the rheumatology clinic in February 2025 after experiencing diffuse trunk pain, skin induration and redness of the chest, abdomen and proximal thighs. The first symptoms started in May 2024, when the patient noticed white skin lesions, pain, redness, mild itching and some hyperpigmented skin areas of the face, upper limbs, trunk and back (Pictures 1, 2).

She experienced muscle aches in the lower extremities after physical activity and denied symptoms of Raynaud's phenomenon or esophageal reflux. She usually took 400 mg ibuprofen tablets once or twice daily to relieve the pain.

The patient's past medical history was notable for pulmonary subsegmental thromboembolism (PE) in July 2024 and has been on anticoagulant treatment with Rivaroxaban 20 mg daily since then. The patient is a homozygous mutation carrier for Methylene tetrahydrofolate Reductase (MTHFR C677C > T), a heterozygous mutation carrier for Plasminogen Activator Inhibitor-1 (PAI-1 4G/

Picture 1. Rash located on the anterior chest wall – hyperpigmentation and whitish spots on the background of diffuse skin thickening.

Picture 2. Anterior abdominal wall – predominantly diffuse skin thickening and erythema.

5G), angiotensin-I converting enzyme Insertion/Deletion (ACE I/D), and Factor XIII. She also had elevated homocysteine levels. The patient reported a family history of PE in her father following surgery. She was on Bisoprolol treatment because of frequent pulse rate. There were no known allergy, risk factors and occupational factors; there are no smoking, alcohol consumption and drug addiction.

In addition to collecting detailed anamnestic data and physical examination, the diagnostic plan included laboratory and instrumental examinations, including skin biopsy if necessary.

Laboratory results exclude the presence of an infectious disease, autoimmune genesis of the identified findings, and/or systemic diseases. Chest X-ray and abdominal ultrasound examination was performed – there were no clinically significant somatic disorders. X-ray of the hands and

fingers revealed early osteoarthritic changes in the distal interphalangeal joints. There was no sclerodactily, nailfold capillaries were normal. The clinical skin findings consisted of violaceous, erythema-infiltrative plaques, we performed dermatology consultation and took skin biopsy.

In the course of the diagnostic search absolutely spontaneous and unprovoked, the patient said that she had taken fossil shell dust for about nine months before the symptoms (from september 2023 to march 2024), purchased from a pharmacy in Sofia. The public Internet information indicates that diatomaceous dust contains fossilized exoskeletons of microscopic algae – diatoms, a type of freshwater phytoplankton that can contain over 90% amorphous silica. (www.himalaya.bg/). The patient took a level tablespoon of the contents of the package, dissolved it in a glass of water, and consumed it once a day, approximately 10 g of the flour daily. She started again taking the diatomaceous flour in May 2024; there were chest pain, increased skin sensitivity and she stopped it permanently.

The instructions for use of diatomaceous dust state that this is “a natural mineral, not a food, medicine or food supplement, that may be used as an additive in animal feed (birds and mammals) for its anti-adhesive effect and has a number of applications in the food industry”. (www.aptekamedea.bg/). Another source states that “Diatomaceous dust is a natural mineral for natural regeneration and strengthening of connective tissue, and is a source of bioavailable silicon in another source. It contains 92% amorphous silica and improves the condition of hair, skin and nails, as well as may be used for toxin cleansing of the body. It is a naturally formed product from the unicellular algae diatoms, which are rich in sulfur compounds and silicon. It is recommended because of beneficial effect after contusions, muscles strengthening, cartilage, joints, detox (purification) and general strengthening of immunity. Its detox effect is based on the millions of negatively charged exoskeletons of diatoms attract positively charged bacteria, protozoa, viruses, endotoxins, pesticides, drug residues, E-Coli bacteria and heavy metals, which are subsequently excreted from the body” (www.remedium.bg/).

The new patient information accelerated the skin biopsy, as in addition to a classic histological examination we decided to proceed with a chemical analysis of the biopsy to quantitatively assess the Si content.

The histological result is presented in Pictures 3–5. The histological diagnosis is scleroderma circumscripta.

Chemical analysis of skin biopsy specimen

We performed instrumental analysis for quantitative assessment of the Si content with Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometer (ICP-MS DRC-e, Perkin Elmer). There was acid decomposition of the sample with nitric acid. We determined the silicon concentration using a quantitative method for analysis with signal reduction with a correction parameter (Rejection Parameter a, RPa) in the dynamic reaction cell (DRC) mode. We analyzed the Si isotopes (^{28}Si , ^{29}Si , ^{30}Si), according to the natural

Picture 3. Histology morphea x septal panniculitis × HE × 100.

Picture 4. Histology hyperkeratosis, acanthosis, coarse collagen bundles, oriented horizontally to the epidermal surface.

Picture 5. Histology morphea × HE × 40.

abundance and the presence of spectral interferences. We performed an external calibration with a series of standard solutions and constructed calibration graphics with

a correlation coefficient at least 0.999 for each of the isotopes. To assess the accuracy of the analysis, we used a certified reference material IAEA-A-11, whose matrix resembles that of the provided sample. The performed ICP-MS analysis of the certified reference material showed a very good agreement between the experimentally determined and certified value. The Si value obtained from the ICP-MS analysis in mg/kg (wet weight) was 380 ± 25 mg/kg (Fig. 1). The chemical analysis of the skin sample showed a silicon content about ten times higher than the norm.

*average value depending on the person's age and diet

Figure 1. Results of Si content [mg/kg] in human skin using ICP-MS.

We assumed that it was scleroderma morphea, due to increased silica intake and localized accumulation in the skin. We prescribed a non-specific antibiotic treatment with Amoxicillin/Clavulanic acid 875/125 mg 3 tablets daily for 7 days, after that – 2 tablets daily for 14 days with some improvement of symptoms.

Discussion

This clinical case is original and is of interest in several points of view – clinical, psychosocial, scientific and regulatory.

- 1. Interest from clinical point of view**, incl. ethio-pathogenesis and therapy: Scleroderma morphea is a rare disease that manifests classically with a benign and self-limiting evolution and is limited to the skin and underlying tissues. A number of cases of scleroderma morphea have described after prolonged inhalation of silica dust, most often as an occupational risk factor. Recent studies have shown that the localized form can affect internal organs and have different morbidity. The treatment should started very early, before complications occur (Careta et al. 2015).

We report the development of scleroderma morphea after oral intake of a product containing silica with an unclear regulatory status for the first time in the scientific literature. During the period of taking diatomaceous dust, the patient took about 2000 g of the product, with a content of over 90–92% silica. We found an accumulation of Si in a skin biopsy more than 10 times above the norm. The case

demonstrate certain causality assessment (WHO 2022, Meyboom et al. 1992), although the intimate mechanism for Si deposition in the skin is unclear. There is no applicable ethiological and pathogenetic treatment in clinical practice. There is no evidence of the presence of a silicon chelator that can extract the accumulated amounts and targeted remove it from the skin.

- 2. Psychosocial aspect:** What could make a healthy consumer to take such products? In the process of collecting anamnesis, we were unable to gather medical and non-medical motives justifying such a personal choice – there is no disease, no doctor's prescription, we did not identify sociocultural, ethnic, religious or any other reasons.
- 3. The last but not at least – scientific and regulatory interest:** the clinical case reveals a series of questions related to public health, concerning medical and pharmaceutical services (care). Some of them are rhetorical: What is the type product diatomaceous dust? Does it have and what is its regulatory status? What is the way to placing to the market? Who is responsible person for placing to the market? Are there any legal requirements for wholesale and retail in the legal chain? Are there rules for the prescription and dispensing regime? Who and how determines its normal and reasonably foreseeable use, how are its health claims justified, are there scientific evidences for them, can it be free advertised to the public, including on pharmacy websites, etc.?

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

Funding

No funding was reported.

Author contributions

All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Author ORCIDs

Iva Parvova <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2775-5326>

Petia Zlateva <https://orcid.org/0009-0009-9729-5426>

Valentina Broshtilova <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2317-0398>

Veronika Mihaylova <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0618-9142>

Valentina Petkova <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6938-1054>

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

References

- Careta MF, Romiti R (2015) Localized scleroderma: clinical spectrum and therapeutic update. *Anais Brasileiros de Dermatologia* 90(1): 62–73. <https://doi.org/10.1590/abd1806-4841.20152890>
- Chung L, Lin J, Furst ED, Fiorentino D (2006) Systemic and localized scleroderma. *Clinics in Dermatology* 24 (5): 374–392. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clindermatol.2006.07.004>
- Cowie R (1987) Silica-dust-exposed mine workers with scleroderma (systemic sclerosis). *Chest* 92(2): 260–262. <https://doi.org/10.1378/chest.92.2.260>
- Bakst R, Kovarik C, Werth VP (2009) A case of localized scleroderma in a sculptor and his wife. *Journal of clinical rheumatology: practical reports on rheumatic & musculoskeletal diseases* 15(8): 399–401. <https://doi.org/10.1097/RHU.0b013e3181c377ea>
- Betta A, Tommasini M, Bovenzi M, Barbone F, Versini W, Romeo L (1994) Scleroderma and occupational factors: a case-control study and analysis of literature. *La Medicina del Lavoro* 85(6): 496–506. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/7731408/>
- Bovenzi M, Barbone F, Betta A, Tommasini M, Versini W (1995) Scleroderma and occupational exposure. *Scandinavian Journal of Work, Environment & Health* 21(4): 289–292. <https://doi.org/10.5271/sjweh.40>
- Foti R, Leonardi R, Rondinone R, Di Gangi M, Leonetti C, Canova M, Doria A (2008) Scleroderma-like disorders. *Autoimmunity Reviews* 7(4): 331–339. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autrev.2007.12.004>
- Haustein UF, Ziegler V (1985) Environmentally induced systemic sclerosis-like disorders. *International Journal of Dermatology* 24(3): 147–151. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-4362.1985.tb05745.x>
- Himalaya (2022) Himalaya. <https://www.himalaya.bg/product/869/diatomichna-prast-zdravnitsa.html>
- Meyboom RHB, Royer RJ (1992) Causality classification in pharmacovigilance centres in the european community. *Pharmacoepidemiology and Drug Safety* 1: 87–97. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pds.2630010207>
- Medea pharmacy (2025) Medea pharmacy. <https://apteka medea.bg/diatomichna-prst-250gr-v1>
- Nikpour M, Morrisroe K, Calderone A, Yates D, Silman A (2025) Occupational dust and chemical exposures and the development of autoimmune rheumatic diseases. *Nat Rev Rheumatol* 21(3): 137–156. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41584-024-01216-3>
- Parks CG, Conrad K, Cooper GS (1999) Occupational exposure to crystalline silica and autoimmune disease. *Environ Health Perspect* 107(Suppl. 5): 793–802. <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp.99107s5793>
- Pedro Gomes J, Shoenfeld Y (2017) Morphea Sculpted in Silica: a case report of limited cutaneous systemic sclerosis in a woman with long-time exposure to silica dust. *The Israel Medical Association journal* 19(7): 459–460. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/28786264/>
- Remedium pharmacy (2025) Remedium pharmacy. <https://remedium.bg/diatomichna-prast-h250-grama-140185/p>
- Riley DS, Barber MS, Kienle GS, Aronson JK, von Schoen-Angerere T, Tugwell P, Kieneg H, Helfandh M, Altmani DG, Sox J, Werthman PG, Moherk D, Risonl RA, Shamseerk L, Kochm CA, Sunn GH, Hanawayo P, Sudakp NL, Kaszkin-Betttagq M, Carpenterr JE, Gagnier JJ (2017) CARE guidelines for case reports: explanation and elaboration document. *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology* 89: 218–235. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2017.04.026>
- Rubio-Rivas M, Moreno R, Corbella X (2017) Occupational and environmental scleroderma. Systematic review and meta-analysis. *Clinical Rheumatology* 36: 569–582. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10067-016-3533-1>
- Rustin MH, Bull HA, Ziegler V, Mehlhorn J, Haustein UF, Maddison PJ, James J, Dowd PM (1990) Silica-associated systemic sclerosis is clinically, serologically and immunologically indistinguishable from idiopathic systemic sclerosis. *The British Journal of Dermatology* 123(6): 725–734. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2133.1990.tb04189.x>
- World Health Organization (WHO) (2022) Uppsala Monitoring Centre. The use of the WHO-UMC system for standardised case causality assessment. Retrieved August 23, 2022. <http://www.who-umc.org/graphics/4409.pdf>